

**Girish Karnad's Search for Indigenous Theatrical Idiom in his
Folk Plays: *Hayavadana, Naga-Mandala, and Flowers***

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Folktales have been an unending source of literature for ages. They are 'short narratives of unknown authorship which have been passed on orally from generation to generation' (Quinn 2004:133). Folk tales are the traditional narratives that inform us about the exploits of our ancestors. They are handed down by word of mouth and subject to the hazards of memory. There have been attempts at keeping the records of these folktales. However, folktales transmitted in printed form are static while those passed on from mouth to mouth are unstable and enjoy "freeplay". They have no fixed form and so they continuously undergo transformation. They have survived through a generation with no trace of their authorship and history. As a result, these tales are used as textual material by authors across the globe.

The folk tradition, that includes folktales and folk art forms, has provided literary artists with important themes and techniques. To literary artists, it offers a great scope to articulate his creativity. Folktales inform him about beliefs, crafts, speech, legends, songs, rituals and stories of a particular culture. They are the great source of entertainment to people who are mostly illiterate. They have, however, flourished among literary population for their simplicity and universality.

In India, folktales are the great source of teaching and preaching material. Elders turn to folktales to teach children lessons in morality, honesty, bravery and humility. Being a multilingual and multicultural nation, India has tremendous corpus of folktales that would suffice many generations. Some of the important folk tales are recorded in the *Panchatantra*, the *Kathasaritasagara*, the *Jataka* tales, and *Vetalpanchavimashika*, and the most recent book by A. K. Ramanujan, *Folktales from India* (1994). These tales sometimes achieve mythic dimension. Some folk stories relate the stories of gods and divine beings. They narrate the achievements of heroic characters from mythologies. However, they lack complexity and universality of myths. So also the heroic nature of myths is substituted by domesticity in folktales.

A. K. Ramanujan, the mentor of Girish Karnad, thinks that we cannot understand the public and domestic culture fully without knowing the folk idiom. All the cultural performances such as classical epic or theatre, or modern films and political rhetoric have their roots in oral traditions and folk forms (xi-xii). The important aspect of folktales is that they are autotelic – they transmit by themselves whenever they are retold. They undergo variations whenever they are transmitted through generations and from places to places (xx).

Folktales have narrative and dramatic quality. They embody great possibilities for their adaptation in performing arts such as drama. The invaluable information embedded in folktales about the people, their gods/goddesses, and rituals, superstitions, songs, proverbs, riddles, worldview of a particular culture is a great source of textual material for playwrights. These folktales have been transmitted through performances. These performances were natural representations of these tales which resulted in the origin of traditional performative art forms (traditional theatrical forms). These indigenous theatres have no theoretical basis. Their practice and performance itself provide us with the theoretical framework or conventions or laws of such performative arts. The memory of their performances in the minds of people helps us document the features of these arts. In India, there were many traditional theatrical forms: *Bhavai*, *Kutiyattam*, *Yakshagana*, *Bhagavatmel and Kucipudi*, *Chau*, *Ramalila*, *Raslila and Krisnalial*, *Yatra*, *Nautanki*, *Pala*, *Tamasa* and so on. However, during the colonial period, these art forms had suffered a planned obsolescence at the hands of so called ‘English literate elites’. They lost popularity due to the arrival of urban enclosed proscenium theatre especially popularised by Parsi theatre groups.

Indian playwrights’ ‘encounter with tradition’ after independence led to various attempts at reinventing and rejuvenating many indigenous forms of drama and performing arts. A very good account or documentation of these forms in *Traditional Indian Theatre* (1980) by Kapila Vatsyayan brought into focus various hitherto unknown theatrical forms from *Kutiyattam* to *Yakshagana*, *Ramalila* to *Yatra*, and from *Bhavai* to *Tamasa*. These forms are indigenous in the sense that they existed before colonialism and survived the onslaught of European theatre. Aparna Dharwadkar views this situation as:

Most of the critical and creative engagement with indigenous forms in the post-independence period has come to center on the folk performance genres popular in various rural regions throughout the country because the category of the “folk” brings into play the most complex range of ideological, political, sociocultural, and aesthetic polarities in contemporary India (*Theatre of Independence*: 2008:311).

Dharwadkar thinks that folk drama is ‘*essentially stylized, antimodern, antirealistic, open air and environment*’ friendly performances and it represents ‘*total theatre*’ which is ‘*antithetical to the seemingly regimented products of the enclosed proscenium stage*’ (312).

It was IPTA (Indian People’s Theatre Association) that set out a program for a ‘cultural awakening of the masses of India’ and rejuvenating the traditional art forms to showcase India’s ‘rich cultural heritage’. A need to reinvent something that is native and known to people for generation (something that is very close to their heart) was felt and this gave an opportunity to the organization such as the IPTA to exploit. They (inspired by Marxist ideology) used this platform to politicise some folk forms such as *Powada*, *Tamasa* (Maharashtra) and *Jatra* (Bengal) to articulate their views against fascism, capitalism and imperialism.

The notion of ‘indianness’ gathered momentum after independence and in all forms of literature there were attempts to create a unique ‘Indian idiom’ reflecting the glorious past of India. In drama, writers such as Chandrashekhar

Kambar, K. N. Panikkar, Habib Tanvir, Girish Karnad, Ratan Thiyam have conspicuously turned to folk and traditional theatrical forms and drawn from sources like myths, folk, *Puranas* and history. According to Girish Karnad, 'the basic concern of the Indian theatre in the post-independence period has been to try to define its 'Indianness' (CP: VI: 315). Hence, these writers experimented with various folk or traditional forms of their regions; and nowadays their names are generally associated with these forms whenever discussion regarding them occurs: Karnad and Kambar with *Yakshagana* and *Bayalata* forms of Karnataka; Panikkar with the folk and classical forms of Kerala; Habib Tanvir with forms of tribals in Chhattisgarh; and Thiyam with the Meitei tribal culture of Manipur.

Girish Karnad employs both themes and techniques of folk theatre in his plays *Hayavadana*, *Naga-Mandala* and *Flowers*. The main plot of *Hayavadana* is taken from popular Sanskrit stories known as "Vetalpanchavimashika" (i.e. twenty five stories that Vetal, the goblin, tells King Vikrama). These stories are part of Somadeva's *Kathasaritsagara*. In all these stories Vetal at the end of his story telling poses a riddle and asks the king to solve it. The king always succeeds in solving the riddle. However, the most immediate source of *Hayavadana* (1971) is Thomas Mann's *Transposed Heads* (1940). *Naga-Mandala* (1990) is based on two oral tales that A. K. Ramanujan told Karnad. And these tales are narrated by an elderly woman while children are being fed in the evening or being put to bed. And the play *Flowers* (2004) is based on a folk tale from the Chitradurga region in Karnataka.

Hayavadana is the second most successful play of Girish Karnad. As mentioned above, the main plot of *Hayavadana* is borrowed from well-known Sanskrit stories – *Vetatpanchavimashika*. The story of 'Transposed Heads' appears at number six in the series of stories told by Vetal. It is a story of Dhavala a young washer-man. He marries a beautiful girl named Madana Sundari. After few days of their marriage, they along with Sundari's brother decided to attend a festival in the city. On their way, they come across a temple of Goddess Durga. Her husband who is a great devotee of Goddess cuts his head as an offering to Her. Horrified at the sight of the gruesome act of his brother-in-law, Sundari's brother too cuts his head. When Sundari sees the two of her dear ones lying dead, she also tries to kill herself. However, the Goddess prevents Sundari from killing her. The Goddess asks her to join the heads of these two men to their respective bodies to bring them back to life. Sundari in her confusion puts the head of her husband on her brother's trunk and vice versa. This creates a very embarrassing situation for Sundari. Now the question is who her real husband is. According to King Vikram, her rightful husband is the one who has her husband's head since head is considered to be the chief of all limbs and one's identity depends upon it. Though the solution to this problem appears to be logically correct, it has a significant incestuous implication. Sundari has to go with a person who has her husband's head and her brother's body.

This story ends with the transposition of heads. But Thomas Mann in his novella, *Transposed Heads*, elaborated and enriched the story by making some additions which actually questions the logic behind the solution offered to Madan Sundari's dilemma in the original tale. He succeeds in avoiding the

problem of incest by inventing characters having no relation. The original version poses a ‘moral problem’ whereas Mann ridicules the very distinction between body and soul, and the supremacy of head over body. Karnad, however, has a different concern, that is, ‘*human identity in a world of tangled relationships*’ (Kurtakoti:1975:vi). He manipulates the very concepts of rational and physical, and presents the never-ending search of human beings to achieve perfection and completeness.

In Thomas Mann’s novella, the spirit is represented by Shridaman, the Brahmin husband, and the flesh by the cowherd friend Nanda. Seeta, Shridaman’s wife, represents the feminine principle. Seeta is happy with the outcome of transposition of heads in the initial period since she has got exactly what she wants - an ideal husband who combines the intellectual of Shridaman and physical strength of Nanda. However, these two men undergo a change as their respective heads transforms their bodies, Shridaman becomes his original self so does Nanda. This transformation disappoints Seeta and she again gets attracted towards Nanda. Hence, the only solution left to this problem is that the two friends must kill each other. In Mann’s story, Seeta’s son is known as Samadhi or Andhaka. He is extremely short sighted and becomes a thinker and scholar (Naik: 2008: 136-137).

Hayavadana is known for the use of *Yakshagana*, a popular folk-art form from Karnataka. There is a use of Bhagavata narrative, invocation, masks, music, appearance of gods and goddesses- etc. Some of the folk motifs and convention also adorn the play like use of masks, story-within-story, talking animals and dolls, miracles etc. So also, into its structure are woven songs rich with folk melodies. It also creates a world of ‘*incomplete individuals, indifferent gods, dolls that speak and children who cannot, a world indifferent to the desires and frustration, joys and sorrows of human beings*’ (Kurtkot: 1975: vii). With *Hayavadana*, Karnad shows his inclination for indigenous theatrical forms. Karnad makes use of the *Yakshagana* to show its applicability and relevance to the contemporary theatre in India.

The play opens with Shri Ganesha *Poojan*. The Bhagavata invokes Shri Ganesha for the successful performance of the play. As in a *Yakshagana* performance, the Bhagavata engages in conversation with the Actor, the *Hasyagana*. The songs of the Bhagavata, Female Chorus and some characters add musical quality to the performance. The inappropriate appearances of things and characters for the audience are not directly shown on the stage. A curtain is put to cover their entry. For example, the entry of Hayavadana is covered with the curtain. Curtains are also used to suggest the entry of Goddess Kali and Padmini’s sacrifice as Sati. Similarly, the climax of the play involves a fight between Devadatta and Kapila as it happens in *Yakshagana* performance. The play ends with thanksgiving to Shri Ganesha for blessing the performance with success.

Naga-Mandala is based on two folk tales from Karnataka. Girish Karnad came to know about the tales from his mentor A. K. Ramanujan. The first tale is about the nature of the oral tales and the second is about a woman, her husband and her snake lover i.e. Naga. The first tale offers commentary on the paradoxical nature of oral tales in general. They have independent existence of their teller and could survive only when they are transmitted from one person to another. Encapsulated within this tale is the tale of Rani who

invents tales to fill the void of her life. It signifies the ‘human need to live by fictions and half-truths’. Girish Karnad says:

Naga-Mandala combines two folk tales. The framing story describes the gathering of the flames in a dilapidated temple after the lamps in the village homes have been extinguished. The gossip of the flames is overheard by a playwright who is condemned to die unless he can keep awake the whole night. The story the playwright hears is about a woman, her husband, and her snake-lover (Tutun:42)

These tales are not just specific to Karnataka as they are found in oral literatures of other regions. The transmission of oral tales is necessary for their survival. It is emphasized in almost all oral tradition. And the second story is of Rani who is confronted with a ruthless husband who visits at daytime and a loving Naga disguised as her husband who comes at bedtime. The echoes of such tales are found in some other similar tales such as the story of *Ahilya* in Valmiki Ramayana. Indra impersonating as her husband, Gautama, devastated her chastity. The use of something magical to win the love of man is also found in Mahabharata. Kunti too like Kurudavva served a mendicant in mind and spirit and in return got some powerful Mantras with the help of which she engaged elemental gods to give birth to powerful sons. She shared that knowledge with Madri, the second wife of her husband. Kurudavva too shares the knowledge of magical roots with Rani and asks her to use them to win the heart of Appanna. Hence, the story of Rani is the story of any woman who goes through the same predicament. In his interview, Girish Karnad quotes A. K. Ramanujan’s remark:

Ramanujan remarked that the tale reflected the experience of the Indian woman in the joint family system. She is confined in her home. The husband is like a stranger during the day; at night he becomes the lover. So there is no complete relationship. He said that this tale also represented such a dichotomy of the woman’s experience. Story-telling provides the mode for expressing the yearning for love of the women often deserted or neglected in the patriarchal social system (Tutun: 43).

In *Naga-Mandala*, Girish Karnad employs the folk dramatic form mixing it with the Frame Narrative Form. It contains the features of the Folk or Oral theatre such as the use of Story Teller, songs, mediating narrative, use of magic, disguise elements, non-human characters, and the presence of the narratee and so on. The play has the ‘Story’ as narrator, songs of the Flames, the magical roots, the Naga disguising as her husband, and the Flames and the Man as narratee

As mentioned above, *Flowers* is based on the legend of Veeranna which was popularized by T. R. Subbanna who used it in his novel, *Hamsageethe* (1952). The story of Veeranna, the priest of Hidimbeshwara temple, is associated with the fort of Chitradurga. The Nayakas, the Poleygars of Chitradurga were very religious and god fearing people. Their each generation built a new temple. Hence, there were many temples. The king used to start and end his journey by paying visits to all these temples. The last

temple used to be the temple of Lord Hidimbeshwara (temple of Shiva), the place where, according to the myth, Bhima vanquished Hidimba.

Veeranna was the priest of the Shiva temple; the first priest being his great grandfather. With the help of bells of each temple, he could know exactly when the King would arrive at the temple. The ringing of melodious bells of nearby Ekanathamma temple used to indicate him about the imminent visit of the King. Then he would start his preparation for worshiping the lingam and offered *Prasad* to the King on his arrival. Only on the day his father passed away, this very routine was broken.

Veeranna had a wife who was not in the best of her health. Hence, he used to fulfill his passion with one of the maids of a court dancer. He used to visit her home after finishing with the priestly duties at the temple. He used to please her by offering her the flowers used for the *pooja*. Veeranna had the court musician Venkatsubbayya as one of his best friends. Venkatsubbayya, also known as Subbanna, used to sing in the court and the temple.

One evening the King could not visit the temple on his stipulated time as there was the wedding ceremony of the Prince. Veeranna too thought that the King would not come that evening. Hence, he performed the *pooja* and went to the maid straightway without waiting for the King. He offered the jasmine garland to the maid who put it in her long hair. Just before they were about to make love, he heard the bells signaling the visit of the King. He just started for the temple taking the garland with him to perform the *pooja* again. He opened the door and started preparation for the *pooja*. Soon the King and the Court musician entered the temple. The priest performed the *pooja* and gave the same jasmine garland to the King as *Prasad*. When the King accepted the flowers in his palms, to his surprise he found a long hair in them. He directly asked the priest whether the lingam had grown long hairs. The priest answered in the affirmative. The King insisted on finding personally whether the lingam really had long hairs. The court musician, however, persuaded him to visit the temple in the morning for inspection as it was too late. The King left the place in anger to come in the morning again to see whether what the priest had said hold truth.

Through the night, the musician and the Priest both prayed to the lingam and requested it to save them from disgrace. A seven headed Serpent appeared to bless them and assured them that they would be saved the next morning.

The King came to the temple in the morning to inspect the Sanctum sanctorum. On his arrival the Priest performed his normal *pooja*. The King asked the musician to check the lingam on his behalf but the later refused. The priest insisted on the King to enter the sanctum sanctorum to see personally whether the lingam had long hair. What happened afterwards; there are two versions available. According to one version, the King dared not to enter the temple and apologized for suspecting the Priest; the second version tells us that the King did enter the temple and found out that the lingam had long hairs. He even checked whether they were real hairs by pulling them. But to his surprise, they turned out to be real as their roots contained the drops of blood.

Though saved by the lingam, Veeranna killed himself by cutting off his head with a sword that afternoon. The musician Subbanna too stopped singing

in the court. The King, as a result, repented over his behavior. He, then, made a stone figure of Veeranna and placed it near the temple. However, according to the tale, the incident was followed by many misfortunes in the region of Chitradurga.

Flowers is a monologue or monodrama in which a priest narrates an important event from his life. The priest directly addresses the audience by sitting near the topmost step of the temple tank. A monologue is meant to reveal the inner most recess of a character-speaker's mind. Here also, the priest reveals his predicament since he is torn between his spiritual love for the Shiva lingam and erotic love for the courtesan Chandravati; between his marital obligations towards his wife and sensual desire for Chandravati; and finally between passion and duty. Like other Karnad's character, he has to make a choice between these two, either the first or the second as Padmini's love for Devdatta and desire for Kapila, and Rani's cruel husband and loving Naga impersonated as her husband.

Girish Karnad banks on folk sources for representing the contemporary reality. Folk sources, unlike myths, are considered to be local and having no universal appeal. Girish Karnad, however, succeeds in bringing the folk tales employed in his plays to the level of universality. He makes them reverberate and resonate with cultural vitality and universal human values, and thus succeeds in finding an indigenous theatrical idiom.

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